

Kersh, N., Laczik, A. & Emms, K. (2023). Building bridges between higher education, vocational learning and employment: Fostering a sustainable ecosystem through practically based higher education (HE) models. In V. Tütlys, L. Vaitkutė & C. Nägele (Eds.), *Vocational Education and Training Transformations for Digital, Sustainable and Socially Fair Future. Proceedings of the 5th Crossing Boundaries Conference in Vocational Education and Training, Kaunas, 25. – 26. May* (pp. 229–236). European Research Network on Vocational Education and Training, VETNET, Vytautas Magnus University Education Academy, Institute of Educational Science. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7821828>

Building Bridges Between Higher Education, Vocational Learning and Employment: Fostering a Sustainable Ecosystem through Practically Based Higher Education (HE) Models

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Abstract

The Higher Education (HE) sector in England demonstrates a tendency of diversification of their provision, specifically through developing strategies to integrate academic and workplace learning. The paper aims to consider a case study of practically-based higher education in a higher education institution in England, as an example of an industry engaged model of higher education which combines academic and practical learning, through cross-disciplinary contextually relevant curricula. The paper reports on the research in progress hence findings at this stage are preliminary and speculative. This paper will specifically focus on the contextual analysis of the case study. The findings indicate that the cross-over between academic studies and practical experiences involves continuous stakeholder collaboration, aiming to foster a deep understanding of student skills and expertise such that they are able to meet unknown challenges in the context of a constantly changing world of work.

Keywords

industry-engaged higher education, employer engagement, workplace learning, ecosystem

1 Context

The paper focuses on the complexities of building bridges between higher education and industry. Specifically it unpacks the ways in which higher education institutions respond to these complexities and develop approaches and strategies when moving their academic provision towards a more work-related provision, to enable students to engage with industries and learn alongside industry professionals. This requires developing and sustaining a unique educational ecosystem underpinned by the links between higher education and industry through integrating theory and practice and fostering stakeholder collaboration and communication.

This research is timely, as contemporary policy and research debates bring attention to an important issue of higher education graduates' work readiness (Kornelakis & Petrakaki, 2020; Bridgstock & Tippett, 2019). It is also timely as many universities introduce programmes that

are supported by industry in a variety of ways and are more practically-based. There is a strong emphasis on the significance of adequately preparing young people for the world of work and equipping them with the skills needed in the labour market to facilitate their employability and career chances (Cranmer, 2006; Prokou, 2008). The paper will focus on one higher education institution case study, specifically exploring the ways, the university has been developing strategies to facilitate stakeholder engagement within a local ecosystem.

2 Research Questions

The focus of the research is on identifying and exploring characteristics, challenges and implications of practically-based and industry engaged HE models operating within an emerging learning ecosystem, that facilitates crossing boundaries between academia and the workplace. The following research questions will be explored:

- What are the key features and components of the ecosystem that facilitate practically-based/industry engaged HE models enabling graduates to transition to the workplace?
- What are the processes, strategies and approaches that universities develop when moving their academic provision towards a more work-related provision?
- How can networks of HE institutions and businesses facilitate, support and sustain these models and processes within the ecosystem?

3 Theoretical considerations

Integrating practically-based and industry engaged approaches in the context of HE requires continuous boundary crossing, specifically through bringing together theory and practice in a meaningful (and innovative) way through strategies underpinned by stakeholder engagement. Such boundaries can be crossed by individuals as they learn at the boundaries of theory and practice as well as by interactions between actors of different practices (Akkerman & Bakker, 2011; Fettes et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2006; Akkerman, 2011). Previous studies have highlighted that integrating theory into practical activities and vice versa, is a multidimensional process that translates into different configurations of crossing boundaries (Kersh, 2015), e.g : (1) boundary crossing and knowledge and skills transfer between education and the world of work; (2) tailoring the curricula to the needs of industries; and (3) motivating students towards the acquisition and integration of subject-based and work-based knowledge.

In the literature, the concept of ‘boundary crossing’ has been traditionally employed in the context of vocational education and training research (e.g. Tuomi-Gröhn & Engeström, 2003; Guile, 2011). Its application to the context of practically based higher education offers opportunities to reconsider the changing nature of the higher education landscape, through exploring its intersections with vocationally related and practice-based learning within the emerging ecosystem that facilitates these innovative practices.

These developments are strongly underpinned by interactions and communications between different stakeholders, which contributes to shaping a unique learning ecosystem, that enables connecting the contexts of work, academic studies and lifelong learning (Spours & Grainger, 2018; Buchanan et al., 2017). Within this study, the concept of ecosystem contributes a better understanding of how individuals, networks and institutions interact, connect, and cross boundaries between learning and working spaces, including digital learning spaces. The concept of ecosystem, used in this study, has been employed in different disciplines as a tool to provide a better understanding of a range of interactions and interdependencies in a variety of contexts, spaces and environments, and there is no universal definition of what constitutes an ecosystem. Hodgson and Spours (2018) note that the concept is helpful to explore how individuals navigate learning and working spaces, while engaging in a range of interactions and communication, and how the spaces and contexts interact and connect through institutional and

other types of cooperation and networking. Spours and Grainger (2018) further bring attention to the emergent Social Ecosystem Model (SEM) which suggests a ‘spatial’ approach linking skills development not only to future work, but also *sustainable* living through what is termed *the working, living and learning nexus*. The multidimensional nature of ecosystems has also been problematised by Buchanan et al. (2017), who observe that a skill ecosystem has many components, where all parts are connected, and changing one part would bring changes to the rest of the ecosystem. Therefore, building and sustaining partnerships between relevant agents or key actors is difficult, and building trust amongst such players takes time and considerable skill. The concept of boundary crossing helps to illuminate the instances of this collaborations and partnerships, as stakeholders navigate and move between contexts and settings (i.e. academic and workplace environments). For our research, this highlights the importance of connecting the worlds of academic learning and workplace experiences, that happen through a range of cooperation among networks and may take place at macro, meso or micro levels, involving communication and collaboration between key actors (stakeholders).

4 Methodology: Case study of practically-based higher education

Our methodology involves undertaking a case study approach to explore and describe innovative and effective approaches of practically-based higher education, in the context of HE in England. It involves both theoretical and empirical research, as follows:

- Literature review and contextual research to identify example of good practice for a case study
- Case study includes 1) contextual analysis and 2) semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders, e.g. senior leadership, lecturers, employers, students.

The literature review phase involved researching practically-based approaches in HE and industry engaged higher education. This has provided a foundation for shaping empirical fieldwork, including: identifying our case studies, relevant stakeholders to be interviewed; making arrangements for interviews/focus groups etc.

Empirical data collection (case study of a university programme representing a model of practically based higher education) has involved undertaking both individual and focus group interviews with key informants, including HE lecturers and curricula leaders; industry representative, students (and other relevant stakeholders)

This research is in progress hence findings at this stage are preliminary and speculative. Data collection will be finalised and systematic analysis under way/findings finalised for the conference. This paper will specifically focus on the contextual analysis of the case study.

5 The case study

Our study focuses on a case of practically based higher education, that involves building bridges between academic leaning and work and developing industry collaborations in a medium-sized university in England (in the Greater Manchester area).

Greater Manchester is a metropolitan area in the North West of England with a population of 2.8 million people. It is the third most populated areas of England. The area has five universities and a College of Music engaging over 100,000 students in 2007. The Greater Manchester College group is an association of 24 local colleges. These colleges offer a selection of courses for 14 and older age group, including higher education courses. While further education colleges offer vocational courses at all levels from the outset, there is a tendency at universities to develop practically-based HE provision. These provisions are based on industry links from local employers. The main industries in the area that employ most of the working population include: 18.4% retail and wholesale; 16.7% manufacturing; 11.8% property and business services; 11.6% health and social work; 8.0% education; 7.3% transport and

communications; 6.7% construction; 4.9% public administration and defence; 4.7% hotels and restaurants; 4.1% finance; 0.8% electricity, gas, and water supply; 0.5% agriculture; and 4.5% other (Wikipedia, accessed: 03.03.2003). The composition of the local industry is important to consider when discussing collaboration of university and industry. Practically-based HE provisions draw on local enterprises, hence their offer will be tailored to locally based industries.

The case study offers a mix of undergraduate and postgraduate courses, with just over 20,000 students in 2018/19. The practically based higher education model involves developing pan-disciplinary clusters of industry collaboration. The model strongly builds on their industry-engaged and demand-led approaches, involving collaboration and communication between a range of stakeholders.

The university made a strong commitment to fostering industry engaged higher education. Partnerships with industry enables the university to produce graduates with relevant knowledge, provide excellent work experience opportunities and create a career-focused curriculum. However, it isn't just our students who benefit from our links with businesses and organisations across the world; through collaboration with businesses of all sizes, we give companies the opportunity to improve their competitiveness and productivity through the better use of knowledge, technology and skills (*extract from The University Business School website*). As further noted in a strategy document, industry collaboration strategy ensures alignment of academic studies, research and enterprise portfolios to employer needs. This is achieved through offering modes of learning which, together with expansion of portfolio of higher technical qualifications, significantly increases flexibility for learners and businesses.

The consideration of the case study has indicated that the approaches that facilitate industry engagement and practically based higher education include both curriculum re-design and targeted (local) industry engagement.

Curriculum re-design

The concept of curriculum redesign has been strongly associated with re-orientating the provision of the different traditional disciplines to ensure they fit suitably with the cross-disciplinary nature of 'Industry Collaboration' (Emms et al., 2021). Particular challenges have been related to redesigning some courses, that have been traditionally perceived as purely theoretical (e.g. English Literature). To address these challenges, and facilitate the reorientation of curriculum design, the university have developed 10 Curriculum Design Principles (CDPs), aiming to foster cross-disciplinary and industry engaged teaching and learning approaches (please see Figure 1, Emms et al., 2021).

Figure 1
Curriculum Design Principles

All existing courses were benchmarked against the CDPs to identify areas for development and curriculum redesign. A number of dedicated workshops were launched, to facilitate the redesign of all taught programmes to ensure the CDPs are embedded into the practice. For instance, ‘a workshop would articulate how the ten Industry Collaboration principles are embedded into a programme, and then agree actions across the team to enhance the Industry Collaboration-readiness of the programme’ (Emms et al., 2021).

Industry engagement: Working with SMEs

Specific attention is paid to working with SMEs, i.e. contextualizing academic learning in local SME ecosystems. Building these relationships with the SME community, facilitates creating regional opportunities for work-related learning and Knowledge Transfer Partnerships (KTPs). This SME eco-system supports industry connectedness strategy and development of potential future strategic partners. (University’s Integrated Report, 2020)

The notion of industry collaboration, enables students to work closely with staff and industry partners on various work-based learning opportunities throughout their courses, such as placements, client-facing projects and other work-related experiences. As noted (Emms et al., 2021) industry relationship has now expanded, breaking down those traditional course silos. Our findings indicate that collaborative partnerships with industries contribute to the development of a local ecosystem, characterised by continuous communication and cooperation between all relevant stakeholders. Facilitating student engagement with industries is at the centre of these partnerships. One example of the development of cross-disciplinary stakeholder engagement is the involvement of the local rugby union club. This partnership was initially developed with the School of Health & Society enabling students to undertake internships, placements and funded masters around sports performance. The partnership has subsequently become cross-disciplinary and cross-departmental involving students from the School of Arts, Media & Creative Technology who have been actively involved in some projects with the rugby club, including the filming and broadcasting of the Rugby Union team’s pre-season warm up matches.

University Information and Legal Knowledge Scheme represents another collaboration within the local ecosystem, providing law students at the University with real world experience. This has been developed in partnership with two local law firms, that offer free legal advice to members of the public. This opportunity enables students to work alongside industry professionals. The university commitment to working and collaborating with local industries has also been illustrated through their engagement with a local media production company. The University current students on the Masters in Media Production are now getting the chance to

get experience with a local media production company, and this represents another meaningful collaboration and stakeholder engagement. This collaboration was developed to enable the company to employ local skilled graduates, and now around 10% of the company's workforce come from directly from the University's broadcast media department. However, the company has not only employed graduates but gives current students the chance to work on their development team as part of their course.

6 Initial findings

The case study suggests that the development of practically-based approaches, is based on a strong conviction that cooperation and collaboration among the key stakeholders represent key features of the ecosystem that facilitates industry engaged HE models enabling graduates to cross boundaries between academic learning and real-life workplace experiences. Engaging students through different forms of learning, workplace and community experiences has been strongly related to addressing their work-related skills, which are both underpinned and influenced by relevant ecosystems and ecologies. The findings indicate that the cross-over between academic studies and practical experiences involves more than simply transferring knowledge and skills from one context to another. It requires an enabling learning ecosystem, underpinned by a range of components, including continuous stakeholder collaboration, curriculum development and integration of theory and practice.

The case study has illustrated some emerging strategies and processes, that the university develops when moving their academic provision towards a more work-related provision. Specific strategies include (1) curriculum re-design and (2) industry engagement, particularly working with SMEs, which contributes to the development of a local ecosystem. The complex processes of building and sustaining such learning ecosystems strongly relates to facilitating meaningful communications among all relevant stakeholders. Within this study, the concept of the learning ecosystem helps to consider the complex methods of communication, strategies and networking approaches that universities develop when moving their academic provision towards a more work-related provision. The consideration of the concept of boundary crossing within a learning ecosystem contributes to a better understanding of the complex systems of communication and collaborations that underpin this process (Buchanan et al., 2017; Edwards, 2011). This includes using both digital and media channels and any other communication processes and practices (Tacchi & Tufte, 2020) that facilitate the links between higher education and industry networks and support and sustain these models and processes within the ecosystem.

The findings indicate that the development of the ecosystem is underpinned by a set of interrelated processes, that have been shaped by the emerging communication and collaboration patterns, between all key stakeholders within the local ecosystem. These complex processes, involve the development of communicative and collaborative ecologies, achieved through shared understanding and facilitating patterns of collaboration and communication between key stakeholders. Within this study, the preliminary findings will be underpinned by empirical evidence from the case study and findings complemented by the systematic analysis.

References

- Akkerman, S. (2011). Learning at boundaries. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 50 (1), 21–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2011.04.005>
- Akkerman, S., & Bakker, A. (2011). Learning at the boundary: An introduction. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 50 (1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2011.04.002>
- Bridgstock, R., & Tippett, N. (Eds.). (2019). *Higher education and the future of graduate employability: A connectedness learning approach*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

- Buchanan, J., Anderson, P. & Power, G. (Eds.). (2017). *Skill Ecosystems*, The Oxford Handbook of Skills and Training. Oxford. 10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199655366.013.21
- Cranmer, S. (2006). Enhancing graduate employability: best intentions and mixed outcomes. *Studies in Higher Education*, 31(2), 169-184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075070600572041>
- Edwards, A. (2011). Building common knowledge at the boundaries between professional practices: relational agency and relational expertise in systems of distributed expertise. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 50, 33-39. doi: 10.1016/j.ijer.2011.04.007
- Emms, K., Laczik, A. & Dabbous, D. (2021). *Rethinking higher education: Case studies for the 21st Century*. London: Edge Foundation
- Fettes, T., Evans, K., & Kashefpakdel, E. (2020). Putting skills to work: It's not so much the what, or even the why, but how.... *Journal of Education and Work*, 33(2), 184-196. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639080.2020.1737320>
- Guile, D. (2011). Workplace learning in the knowledge economy: The development of vocational practice and social capital. In M. Malloch, L. Cairns, K. Evans, & B. O'Connor (Eds.), *The SAGE Handbook of Workplace Learning* (pp. 385-394). SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446200940.n28>
- Hodgson, A. & Spours, K. (2018). A social ecosystem model: conceptualizing and connecting working, living and learning in London's 'New East', ELVET Programme Research Briefing 3. London: Centre for Post-14 Education and Work, UCL Institute of Education.
- Kersh, N. (2015). Rethinking the learning space at work and beyond: The achievement of agency across the boundaries of work-related spaces and environments. *International Review of Education*, 61(6), 835-851. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11159-015-9529-2>
- Kornelakis, A., & Petrakaki, D. (2020). Embedding employability skills in UK higher education: Between digitalization and marketization. *Industry and Higher Education*, 34(5), 290-297. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950422220902978>
- Prokou, E. (2008). The Emphasis on Employability and the Changing Role of the University in Europe. *Higher Education in Europe*, 33(4), 387-394. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03797720802522593>
- University's Integrated Report, 2020 (2020). Salford Integrated Report. <https://www.salford.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2020-12/IntegratedReport2020.pdf>
- Spours, K., & Grainger, P. (2018). A Social Ecosystem Model: A new paradigm for skills development? [Digital scholarly resource]. <https://t20argentina.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/T20-Social-Ecosystem-Model-revised-KS-2.pdf>
- Tacchi, J., & Tuft, T. (Eds.). (2020). *Communicating for change: Concepts to think with*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Tuomi-Gröhn, T., & Engeström, Y. (Eds.). (2003). *Between school and work: New perspectives on transfer and boundary-crossing* (1st ed). Pergamon.

Biographical notes

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